

FOREIGN INVASIONS AND GLOBAL REACTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EUROPEAN INVASION OF PRE-COLONIAL AFRICAN POLITIES AND RUSSIAN INVASION OF UKRAINE

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Abstract: Modern human history is replete with invasions of states by states, and such invasions have elicited diverse global reactions. From the 15th century upward for instance, Europeans invaded precolonial African polities in their quest to chiefly satisfy their economic appetite. In 2022, Russia invaded a fellow European country – Ukraine, in her quest to wade off NATO expansionism and invariably, to promote her expansionist policy. While the latter has elicited global condemnations and severe sanctions on Russia and Russians; the former received justifications mainly from renowned and reverend European erudite scholars. As a theory in international relations, Realism views these invasions and the attendant discrepancies in global responses as inevitable due to the selfish nature of nation-states. To right historical wrongs and heal lingering historical wounds, this paper recommends that European countries who invaded, destroyed, and pillaged precolonial African states should, as a matter of urgency, establish an Afro-Euro Commission with special trust fund, aimed at reconciliation, restitution, reconstruction and development of affected African territories.

Keywords: War, Russian Invasion, European Invasion, Pre-colonial African Polities.

1. INTRODUCTION

No permanent friend and no permanent enemy, but permanent interest is a popular axiom in politics and international relations. By implication, interest is the purveyor of states' drive in international politics, and they deploy different means (including amorality) in the actualization of their respective interests. Hence, the application of Thomas Hobbes' social contract theory to international relations, will no doubt portray states as essentially selfish and brutish entities, who subscribe to war by passions rather than intellect in the pursuit of their individual national interests. Consequently, states have become wolves to states as they do, and have continued to invade others to protect their individual or collective national objectives. Thus, from historical lane, states have witnessed various degrees of devastating invasions which have rendered human lives and society solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short (Hobbes, 1952).

Invasion here connotes war which is one of the world's oldest notorious organized endeavors, predating civilizations like writing. Though an old event, the meaning of war remains clouded in the minds of students as the term has been used in diverse contexts. For instance governments, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), international organizations, etc. do claim to engage in: external invasion, "the war on poverty, drug wars, trade wars, the war on terrorism," etc. Nevertheless, this paper focuses on invasion or the war that involves conflict, including armed confrontation, between nation-states and other actors (Chun, 2002, p. 1).

What then is war or invasion; and why do states invade states? While Tzu (1971, p. 63) constructed war as "a matter of vital importance to the State"; Tse-Tung (1963, p. 76) coined it as the highest form of conflict for conflicts resolution between classes, nations, states, or political groups since "the emergence of private property and of classes". To Clausewitz (1984, pp. 75 & 78) war can be defined as "an act of force to compel our enemy to do our will" or as "merely the continuation of policy by other means".

From the first two definitions above, states invade others because they see war as a key means to resolve class struggle and effect desired social revolution. Hence, it has been opined "that the purpose of war is to make peace". By Clausewitz's definition, states go to war or invade others by actual or threatened deployment of military assets, in order to force their opponent(s) to promote their respective national interests. Thus, a state might invade another in order to maintain its identity or sovereignty by thwarting "another country's ability to project its power beyond its borders". Going by Clausewitz's second definition, nations invade others for political objectives – "to influence trade routes, alliances, balance of power issues, or other question..." (Chun, 2002, pp. 2, 6, 25, & 40). Hence, it has earlier been argued that nations go to war for the sakes of "honor, fear, and interest" (Thucydides, as cited in Kagan, 1995, p. 8).

The above scholarly perceptions of war do not only avail a clear picture of why states invade others, they also create a smooth pathway to examine and understand why Europeans invaded pre-colonial African states, and why Russia invaded Ukraine. The usefulness therein, is that they enable one to evaluate whether the disparities in global responses are justifiable or otherwise. This paper thus, focuses on European invasion of pre-colonial African states and Russia's invasion of Ukraine, as well as their respective resultant global reactions. In the case of Russia's invasion, the paper focused on global reactions from International organisations, states, and world leaders; while that of the former focused mainly on global reactions from renowned and reverend erudite European scholars. The paper adopts realism as theoretical framework, comparative approach to study, as well as content analysis as tool for data collection to examine and analyse global reactions to both invasions. In conclusion, it made feasible suggestions aimed at addressing such disparities in global responses to foreign invasions.

Theoretical Framework: Realism

Realism as a theory in International Relations, highlights the flaws (egoism, appetite for power, and inability to trust others) in human nature as the root rationales behind foreign invasions and variations in global responses. Due to these flaws, realism holds that humans are basically held hostage to repetitive patterns of behaviour, thereby cascading into predictable outcomes. More so, since humans are organised into states, their imperfect nature, by logical extension, impacts on state's behaviour. Machiavelli (1991) for instance, instructed that a leader who must ensure the security and survival of his state should be a lion (powerful and destructive) and a fox (deceptive or diplomatic) – state's tools for the conduct of foreign policy. That is, he should obey the 'ethics of responsibility', and eschew morality. Simply put, he should be good when possible, but he must also be disposed to unleash violence when necessary to ensure his state's survival. Similarly, Morgenthau (1948) opined that since "every political action is directed towards keeping, increasing or demonstrating power", leaders should therefore, place premium on power over morality – they should discard morality in foreign policymaking as it engenders possible "destruction or domination of a state by a competitor" (Antunes & Camisão, 2017, p. 16).

Conversely, Waltz (1979), who modernized realism and invented an empirical brand known as 'neorealism' or 'structural realism', argued that state's foreign policies are not influenced by unprovable imperfections in human nature. Rather, they are determined by the anarchic nature of the international system, as well as the relative power of states "when measured against other states" (Antunes & Camisão, 2017, p. 17).

In summary, Antunes and Camisão (2017, p. 15) highlighted the basics of realism to include: first, realism believes that the state is the principle actor in international relations. Other actors such as individuals and organisations do exist, but they

wield limited power. Second, the state is a unitary actor – it speaks and acts with one voice precisely in the eras of war in order to achieve its national interests. Third, decision-makers, irrespective of their political persuasions, are rational actors, as they all recognise the reality that only rational made decisions facilitate the pursuit of national interests or enable them to manage their state’s affairs so as to survive in a competitive milieu. Lastly, states live in an anarchic atmosphere sequel to “the absence of anyone being in charge internationally” or ‘no one to call’ for helps in times of international emergency. That is, states live in a somewhat Hobbesian state of nature characterised by the nonexistence of a global government with absolute sovereignty. To ensure self-preservation or survival, the state thus, becomes selfishness, desire power, and distrust others.

From the above, it can be deduced that European invasion of precolonial African polities, and Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, coupled with the variations in global responses, as subsequently examined in this work, were influenced by selfishness, the need for survival – security and development, anarchic nature of the international system, as well as state’s relative powers when measured against others.

European Invasion of Precolonial African Polities: Reasons and Impacts on Africa

In the case of European invasion of precolonial African polities, several verifiable causal factors have been adduced. According to Odemwingie (2021, pp. 53-56) these ranged from European need for new market; quest for raw materials (agricultural products and mineral resources) for domestic and industrial consumptions; the need to invest surplus capital in new overseas territories with cheap labour, cheap raw materials, and quick return on investment; the discovery of minerals deposits in Africa such as the 1867 discovery of diamonds in Kimberley (Hyde, 2006) and the 1886 discovery of the world’s largest gold deposit in Rand, South Africa; the need to tackle the massive unemployment pogrom in Britain, France, Germany, and Italy due to Industrial Revolution – the era of invention of industrial machines which displaced and replaced industrial workers; humanitarian reasons – the quest to eradicate slavery and extend the material and spiritual benefits of European civilization to Africans (July, 1968); the prevalence of racial theories which championed European superiority and divine mission to rule over other races precisely the Negroes; supremacy struggle amongst European countries or the need for national prestige; to the 1884-1885 Berlin Conference which did not only legalised Europeans’ illegal occupation of territories in Africa, but also laid down the conditions for such occupation.

European invasion of Africa based on the above rationales, yielded mixed impacts of which the adverse effects far outweighed the benefits. As aptly observed by Odemwingie (2021, pp. 77-80) “it led to the ignominious elimination of African traditional rulers by deaths, deportations, or replacements with stooges who allied with the occupying European powers”. In Ivory Coast, the French thoroughly annihilated most African chiefs to establish French rule. The British invaders: in Opobo kingdom in 1887, banished King Jaja to West Indies; in Itsekiri kingdom in 1894, ousted and exiled Chief Nana Olomu to Calabar, and later to Accra; in Benin Kingdom, sequel to the Benin Massacre of 1897, deposed and deported Oba Ovonramwen to Calabar where he later died in 1914; forced the Sultan of Sokoto, Muhammadu Attahiru I, to flee from his Caliphate, and later killed him in a battle in 1903 (Falola, 2009); deported *Asantehene* Prempeh I of Ashanti Kingdom to Sierra Leone, and later to Seychelles’ Islands; “defeated, deposed, and replaced Kabaka Mwanga of Buganda with his infant son (Daudi Cwa), and subsequently captured and exiled him alongside his guerrilla ally – King Kabarega of Bunyoro, to Seychelles in 1899” (Kasfir, 2008; Reid, 2017); etc.

It resulted into the destructions of pre-colonial African polities like the kingdoms of Ashanti, Benin, Bunyoro, and Buganda; the Sokoto Caliphate, etc.; and their subsequent replacements with the colonial states of Gold Coast (now Ghana), Uganda, Nigeria, etc. More so, it cascaded into the division of Africans of the same ethnic group into two or more colonial states. For instance, the Somalis were split into British Somaliland, Italian Somaliland, French Somaliland (now Djibouti), Ethiopia, and Kenya (Thomson, 2010); “the Ewes into German (later French) Togoland and Anglophone Ghana; the Yorubas into Nigeria and Dahomey; the Bakongos into Francophone Congo Brazzaville, Belgian Congo Kinshasa (DRC), and Busophone Angola”; etc. Conversely, it also led to the forceful integration of heterogeneous and/or rival ethnic groups to create most modern African states. “These incompatible unions have continued to trigger political instability like irredentism – Somalia’s 1970s war with Ethiopia aimed at annexing the Ogaden area populated by ethnic Somalis in order to ‘house’ all Somalis within the borders of one sovereign state, genocides, civil wars, ethnic competitions, national disunity, etc. in post-colonial African states” (Thomson, 2010; Odemwingie, 2021, pp. 78 & 79).

The atrocities perpetrated by Europeans during the invasion of Africa led to the disorganization of African social life and depopulation in several territories. For instance, in Ivory Coast, scores of villages were destroyed by French imperialists;

while the cruel government of king Leopold II decreased the Congolese population from twenty million to an estimate of over ten million between 1885 and 1908 (Johnson, 2014; Odemwingie, 2021).

The invasion created room for the callous unequal exchange and exploitation of Africans, their labour, lands, agricultural produce, and mineral resources for European benefits (Odemwingie, 2021). For instance “the cotton grown by African... peasant farmers was fed into the Lancashire textile mills, via the flourishing port of Liverpool, and the cloth which the mills produced was exported back to Africa by European trading companies. However, while the price which the producer received for his cotton fluctuated widely, and often downwards, the price which he had to pay for imported cloth constantly increased. *“The unequal and exploitative nature of this exchange... contributed to the capitalist development of Europe at Africa’s expense”* (Tordoff, 2002, p. 26).

As further highlighted by Odemwingie (2021, p. 80), European invasion and the subsequent colonization of Africa did not only “paved the way for the impoverishment of Africans precisely in areas where the colonial armies systematically looted and destroyed invaluable African works of art, palaces of African chiefs and monarchs, towns, and villages”; it also eroded African indigenous languages as official languages of precolonial African states, and replaced them with “the alien languages of their ex-colonial powers for official and business purposes”. For instance, French became the official language in twenty-one African countries, English in twenty, and Portuguese in five, while countries like Cameroon and Mauritius adopted both English and French as official languages (Hyde, 2006).

Russian Invasion of Ukraine: Reasons and Impacts on Ukraine

On February 24, 2022, Russian President, “Vladimir Putin unleashed the biggest war in Europe since” WWII “with the justification that modern, Western-leaning Ukraine was a constant threat and Russia could not feel “safe, develop and exist””. Thus, Putin’s initial plan via his “special military operation” or “noble” cause, was: first, to overrun Ukraine and depose its government in order to end for good its desire to join NATO; and secondly, to “demilitarise and de-Nazify Ukraine”, so as to protect people subjected to “eight years of bullying and genocide by Ukraine's government”. However, Putin denied Russia has “plan to occupy the Ukrainian territory” or “to impose anything on anyone by force” (Kirby, 2022, pp. 1 & 2).

Nevertheless, Russia’s war in Ukraine has adversely affected the thirty-one years old European country. In the economic sphere for instance, Anna Bjerde – World Bank Vice President for the Europe and Central Asia region, stated that “Russian invasion is delivering a massive blow to Ukraine’s economy and it has inflicted enormous damage to infrastructure” (Bjerde, as cited in World Bank Press Release, 2022, p. 2). Thus, it has been predicted that “Ukraine’s economy is expected to shrink by an estimated 45.1 percent this year [2022], although the magnitude of the contraction will depend on the duration and intensity of the war” (World Bank Press Release, 2022, pp. 1-2).

On humanitarianism, it has been observed that the invasion has already triggered “the largest refugee crisis in Europe since World War II” (World Bank Press Release, 2022, p. 4). According to Anna Bjerde (Bjerde, as cited in World Bank Press Release, 2022, p. 2) “the magnitude of the humanitarian crisis unleashed by the war is staggering” as millions of Ukrainians “are suffering and coping with an extreme situation.” Nevertheless, Kirby (2022) reported that the invasion has led to the displacement of more than 11 million people within and outside Ukraine. Of this figure, the IOM survey on displacement, released on April 21, showed that over 7.7 million people (many who are particularly patients with chronic illnesses, the vulnerable, pregnant and breastfeeding women, the aged, the disabled, and people directly affected by violence) have been internally displaced since the war began. Thus, cascading into urgent needs for monetary, food, shelter, transportation, hygiene items, psychosocial, medicines and health services supports (IOM, 2022, March 21; IOM, 2022, April 5; IOM, 2022, April 22).

As of April 12, 2022, the United Nations estimated the human cost of Russia’s invasion of Ukraine (excluding military casualties) to be 4,450 civilian casualties – 1,892 killed and 2,558 injured. Howbeit, the UN “believes that the actual figures are considerably higher”, but getting the exact figures have been hampered by delayed reports “from the battlefield and efforts to verify existing reports”. On the other hand, the Ukrainian authorities claimed that 720 dead bodies had been recovered in the Kyiv region; 700 in Chernigiv; 400 in Severodonetsk; between 20,000 and 22,000 in Donetsk; etc. Conversely, suspiciously inflated and unverified military death toll has been released by both Russia and Ukraine. Sequel to Ukraine claims that its forces had killed 19,600 Russian military personnel since the invasion started on February 24th;

Moscow retorted on March 25th that it has only lost 1,351 soldiers, while its troops had killed at least 14,000 Ukrainian military personnel (France24, 2022, p. 1).

In its geo-political sphere, Russia's war in Ukraine has led to the annexation of four eastern Ukraine's regions – Donetsk, Luhansk, Kherson and Zaporizhzhia – by Russia via the 23rd to 27th September, 2022 referendums which have been “condemned as a sham by Ukraine and many western countries” (BBC News, 2022, p. 2).

The above devastations, and perhaps more to come if the invasion carries, prompted Asli Demirgüç-Kunt – World Bank Chief Economist for Europe and Central Asia, to lament that “crises can cause widespread economic damage and set back years of per capita income and development gains” (Demirgüç-Kunt, as cited in World Bank Press Release, 2022, p. 3).

A Comparative Analysis of Global Responses to Russian Invasion of Ukraine and European Invasion of Precolonial African Polities

a. Global Responses to Russian Invasion of Ukraine

The 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine has led to widespread global reactions in the form of series of condemnations and sanctions against Russia, as well as series of aids to Ukraine from states, international organisations, NGOs, state and non-state actors, etc. For instance, to ensure Russia pay the price for this aggression, UEFA stripped her of Champions League final over the attacks (Al Jazeera News, 2022); the World Bank Group, from the inception of the invasion, mobilized an emergency financing package of \$925 million (a part of the \$3 billion package) to support Ukraine in the payments of pensions for the elderly, wages for hospital workers, and social programmes for the vulnerable (World Bank Press Release, 2022); the UN General Assembly suspended Russia from the U.N. Human Rights Council over reports of "gross and systematic violations and abuses of human rights" in Ukraine (Nichols, 2022, p. 2); the African Union, on the day of the invasion, unequivocally called on Russia to respect "the territorial integrity and national sovereignty of Ukraine" (Cocks, 2022, pp. 2-3); while ECOWAS (five days after the invasion) condemned the invasion, urging both countries “to agree to a ceasefire... resolve the crisis through dialogue... [And] ensure the safety of Africans living in Ukraine” (Africanews, 2022, pp. 1-2).

Similarly, the European Union – a body of 27 European countries, barred export of specific refining technologies from Europe to Russia; closed its airspace to Russian aircraft, including the private jets owned by Russian oligarchs; banned Russian state-owned television network (Russia Today) and news agency (Sputnik); barred the importation of cement, mineral fuels, tobacco, wood and timber, iron and steel for Russian ally – Belarus; froze assets of Russian President, Vladimir Putin and his foreign minister, Sergey Lavrov in European; (Al Jazeera News, 2022); and restricted “the sale of "golden passports," which allow wealthy Russians to gain citizenship in another country in exchange for an investment.” In the same vein, France vowed to go after luxury goods like real estate, yachts, luxury vehicles and financial assets owned by Russians targeted by European sanctions (Toh, *et al*, 2022, p. 4).

On its part, the United States targeted: Russian military end-users, including its defence ministry; as well as the “Russia's oil refining sector” by placing ban on “the export of specific refining technologies, making it tougher for Russia to modernise its oil refineries.” The US also imposed sanctions on the state-owned Russian Direct Investment Fund in order to cripple her financial capacity to finance the invasion; blocked export on technology including “wide restrictions on semiconductors, telecommunication, encryption security, lasers, sensors, navigation, avionics and maritime technologies” in order to severely limit Russia's ability to advance its military and aerospace sector; barred Russian financial institutions including the Russian Central Bank from making transactions in American dollars; and in conjunction with the EU, the UK, and Canada, barred certain Russia's banks from the SWIFT international payments system – the high security network that enables payments amongst 11,000 financial institutions in 200 countries; etc. Apart from Russia, the US also imposed sanctions on 24 Belarusian individuals and firms including two key Belarusian state-owned banks, nine defence firms, and seven regime-linked elites and officials (Toh, *et al*, 2022; Al Jazeera News, 2022, March 3, pp. 2-3).

Canada in response to “Russia's reckless and dangerous military strike”, cancelled all export permits; sanctioned 62 Russians and entities, including members of the elite (like the defence minister, finance minister, and justice minister) and major banks; prioritised immigration applications for Ukrainians, who wish to migrate to Canada (Prime Minister Justin Trudeau, as cited in Al Jazeera News, 2022, p. 8); etc.

The United Kingdom banned Sberbank (Russia's largest bank) from clearing payments in Sterling. The UK also threatened to: freeze full assets of three Russian banks (Otkritie, Sovcombank and VEB) including Russian state bank (VTB); prevent

Russian state and private companies from fund raising in the UK; ban Russia's national airline (Aeroflot) from landing in the UK; block exportation of certain technologies to Russia, precisely in telecommunications, electronics, and aerospace sectors; sanction Belarus for its role in the invasion (Toh, *et al*, 2022, p. 12; Al Jazeera News, 2022, March 3, pp. 2-3); etc. As Prime Minister Boris Johnson clearly stated, the UK "will continue on a remorseless mission to squeeze Russia, from the global economy, piece by piece. Day by day, and week by week," (Johnson, as cited in Toh, *et al*, 2022, p. 12).

Switzerland, in a sharp deviation from her traditional neutrality, in support of Western values, and in reaction to "Russia's unprecedented military attack on a sovereign European country", adopted all the sanctions imposed on Russia, its people (comprising Putin, Prime Minister Mikhail Mishustin and Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov), and companies including freezing of their assets. Its neighbour – Germany, on her part, halted certification of the Nord Stream 2 gas pipeline (Al Jazeera News, 2022; Swiss Federal President Ignazio Cassis, as cited in Toh, *et al*, 2022, p. 5). In a "much more sensitive" response against "the aggressive policy of Russia", Czech Republic banned Russian airlines from flying to its geographic entity; planned to exit from two international banks established during the Soviet era (Prime Minister Petr Fiala, as cited in Al Jazeera News, 2022, p. 9); etc.

Japan in a display of its intolerance to Russian aggression in Ukraine, sanctioned Russian financial institutions and individuals; froze Putin's assets; banned exports of military-use goods like semiconductors; etc. Its neighbour – South Korea, equally collaborated with her western allies to restrict exports of strategic items to Russia, as well as to block selected Russian banks from the SWIFT international payments system (Al Jazeera News, 2022; Toh, *et al*, 2022); while Taiwan, the world's largest contract chipmaker, threatened to "join democratic countries to jointly impose sanctions" on Russia for her "act of invasion" (Premier Su Tseng-Chang, as cited in Al Jazeera News, 2022, p. 10).

Australia also imposed sanctions on Russian oligarchs, whose economic weight constituted "strategic significance to Russia and over 300 members of the Russian Duma, their parliament", who voted to authorise the deployment of Russian troops into Ukraine; imposed travel bans and targeted financial sanctions on eight members of Russian Security; etc. In alliance with the USA, it equally threatened to extend similar sanctions to Belarusian individuals and entities who supported Russia (Prime Minister Scott Morrison, as cited in Toh, *et al*, 2022, p. 7; Al Jazeera News, 2022). Conversely, its neighbour (New Zealand) also imposed travel bans on Russia and barred trade to its military and security forces in order to ensure that Russia "face the condemnation of the world" for its "blatant use of military might and violence" (Prime Minister Jacinda Ardern, as cited in Toh, *et al*, 2022, p. 7; Al Jazeera News, 2022, p. 11).

Following the above series of sanctions, the Russia's stocks and currency tanked, and its stock market was closed. Its currency (Ruble) slides as high as 30% against the dollar, while its central bank more than doubled interest rates to 20% (Toh, *et al*, 2022).

b. Global Responses to European Invasion of Precolonial African Polities

Global responses to European invasion of precolonial African states were nothing, but mere constructions by Eurocentric scholars aimed at downplaying African contributions to world civilization in order to justify the invasions. Hegel (1991) for instance in his book – *The Philosophy of History*, classified humanity into historical peoples (those who have contributed to the human civilization) and non-historical people (Africans, who had no input in mankind's development). "To him, the history of the world travels from East (Asia as starting point) to West (Europe as the end point of history). Thus, he concluded that Africa has no history because she has no development to showcase" (Adeoti, 2014; Odemwingie, 2021, pp. 2-3). In what can be ascribed as his response to European invasion of precolonial African polities, Hegel opined:

At this point we leave Africa, not to mention it again. For it is no historical part of the world; it has no movement or development to exhibit. Historical movements in it – that is in its northern part – belong to the Asiatic or European world. Carthage displayed there an important transitional phase of civilization; but, as a Phoenician colony, it belongs to Asia. Egypt will be considered in reference to the passage of the human mind from its Eastern to its Western phase, but it does not belong to the African spirit. What we properly understand by Africa, is the Unhistorical, Undeveloped Spirit, still involved in the conditions of mere nature, and which had to be presented here only as on the threshold of the World's history (Hegel, 1991, p. 99).

Similarly, Perham (1951) responded that precolonial Africa was a multicellular tissue of tribalism, as well as the largest area of primitive poverty enduring into the modern age. In her words:

Until very recent perpetration of Europe, the greater part of the continent [Africa] was without the wheel, the plough or the transport animal; without stone houses or clothes except skins; without writing and so without history (Perham, 1951, p. 638).

Aligning with Hegel's and Perham's submissions, Trevor-Roper, an Oxford historian, added:

Perhaps, in the future, there will be some African history to teach. But at the present there is none, or very little: there is only the history of the Europeans in Africa. The rest is largely darkness and darkness is not the subject of history (Trevor-Roper, as cited in Mazrui, 1978, p. 94).

In an earlier assertion, Hume in his 1758 *Essay XXI: Of National Characters*, racially painted Africans as "low people without education and symptoms of ingenuity". To him:

You may obtain anything of the Negroes by offering them strong drink; and may easily prevail with them to sell, not only their children, but their wives and mistresses, for a cask of brandy... [Thus] I am apt to suspect the Negroes to be naturally inferior to the whites. There scarcely ever was a civilized nation of that complexion, nor even any individual eminent either in action or speculation. No ingenious manufactures amongst them, no arts, no sciences (Hume, 1987, pp. 134 & 372).

In the same vein, Breasted opined:

On the south of the Northwest Quadrant lay the teeming black world of Africa, as it does today. It was separated from the white race by the broad stretch of the Sahara Desert. Sometimes the blacks of inner Africa did wander along [the Nile] into Egypt, but they only came in small groups. Thus cut off by the desert barrier and living by themselves, they remained uninfluenced by civilization by the north, nor did they contribute appreciably to this civilization (Breasted, 1937, pp. 44-45).

In total submission to the above Eurocentric assertions, Hanna in his work – *European Rule in Africa*, retorted:

Yet it is virtually certain that conditions in Africa would still be roughly what they were a century ago, had it not been for the introduction of European administration, European instruction, and contact with the European economy (Hanna, 1961 p. 11).

2. CONCLUSION

From the above, it can be inferred that global responses to both invasions were based on vested national cum multilateral interests. Russia's invasion of Ukraine attracted worldwide crucifying responses on Russia and Russians; while European invasion of Africa received justified and glorified responses, precisely from renowned and revered Eurocentric scholars. Western powers with their global influences and crony states, condemned Russia for invading Ukraine due to their vested interest – expansion of NATO sphere of influence by admitting Ukraine into its fold so as to deploy "strike weapons near Russia's borders" in the Baltics, Central and Eastern Europe (Putin, as cited in Kirby, 2022, p. 6). Conversely, European invasion of Africa was justified due to their collective global influences – their superior powers when measured against those of precolonial African polities; and their economic interests aimed at their respective developments at the expense of under-developing Africa. Although these invasions and the attendant global responses occurred centuries apart, the discriminatory global reactions bring to mind the 1954 lamentation of Chief Remi Fani Kayode, who asserted:

Besides the Jews, we the black people of the world, are the most hated by the present world powers; No pact or treaty with righteousness, with justice, with equity is ever applicable to us; we are expressly exempted... (Kayode, p. 32, 1954).

Reporting similar sentiments harboured by a senior African diplomat and Chris Ogunmodede, an associate editor at World Politics Review, Cocks wrote:

It's a feeling that we are where superpowers practise their games. How we experience it doesn't matter to them. What they care about is their power... When we [Africans] have a problem, we're on our own; when there's an 'international problem', as defined by the West, then it's a global problem... Everybody treats us like pawns (a senior African diplomat and Ogunmodede, as cited in Cocks, 2022, pp. 4-5).

If what is good for the goose is indeed good for the gander, then all states and peoples should be treated with justice, equity and fairness. Any invasion by any conscienceless power should be vehemently condemned by all. To this end, European countries that invaded, destroyed, and pillaged precolonial African states should, as a matter of urgency, establish an Afro-

Euro Commission with special trust fund aimed at reconciliation, restitution, reconstruction and development of affected African territories. The Commission *inter alia*, shall partner with African governments in affected African territories to facilitate the repatriation of stolen artefacts and the construction of modern museums to house them; and in the development of key sectors like education (human capital development and scholarship programmes), transportation, agriculture, electricity, tourism, art and culture.

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